

Remediation of Concrete Structures – Technical Solutions meeting monument preservation demands

“Smart Repair” – A new approach to Concrete Repair in monuments

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Historic Monuments, made of reinforced concrete, make completely new requirements on the methods of repair and remediation. In particular the large scale measures of surface preparation, e. g. sand blasting and high pressure water jets, complete surface coatings with mortars etc., cause severe changes in the special characteristics of a historic monument. In consequence, their application in the course of a restoration must be avoided.

It must always be our aim, to repair only very locally the affected areas.

In Europe, the repair of concrete buildings normally follows the national guide lines, in the last years also the new European Standard EN 1504 1-10. This standard describes both the requirements on the products and systems used in the repair of concrete as also the principles and methods of concrete repair and protection. The first steps of the assessment and planning also in restoring historical concrete, follow exactly the principles of EN 1504.

Table 1: Systematics of planning according to EN 1504-9 (after RAUPACH, 2005)

Sometimes the efforts for the documentation of the situation are even higher than in other cases, treating buildings that are not classified.

Legend:

	Visible reinforcement		Quickscan
	Cracks		Rock pockets
	Scales		Drilling core
	Surface defect		Sample, powder
	Cavities		Figures in text
	Rest of wood		

Fig. 1: Detail from the documentation of deterioration on the ore bunker in the Voelklingen Ironworks

In the further steps, defining the methods for remediation, there are often certain discrepancies found, due to the demands of monument preservation.

During the last 10 years, some rules have been developed that meanwhile serve as guidelines for the smart repair of historic concrete buildings.

- The complete surface of the monument has to be preserved – in the same way as a monument of natural stone: The surface, as the “skin” of the building, is the witness of the ancient craftsman’s treatment.
- Any structures and characteristics of the concrete which are part of the building design
- Any structures and characteristics which are due to faults in the execution of construction work
- Even cracks, cavities and other surface defects belong to the monument
- All structures which are a consequence of the “lifetime influences” have to be preserved, e. g. bullet holes,

Beyond that, the ancient concrete, often with an age of 100 years and more, has a composition that differs significantly from our modern types of concrete. Here, in our examples, it is particularly the sands and gravels in the concrete aggregate that result from the iron production: blast furnace slag. It gives a typical shade of colour, and is highly soluble in acid. As a result, any chemical analysis of the concrete will be incorrect, when based on dissolving in hydrochloric acid. By x-ray analysis as well as microscopical examination the existence of the blast furnace slag as sand and gravel was proved.

As we had to find out the right composition and the grain size curve of the historic concrete, it was indispensable to find another way – we chose a kind of image analysis, specially adapted to this purpose. The drilling cores were cut in thin discs, grinded and polished. By the aid of the image analysis, more than 5000 points per sample were counted and assigned to the different types of sand and the different grain sizes.

As a result, a grain size curve was received, which built the base for the composition of the new concrete.

Several other methods of analysis were applied, e.g. compressive strength, water absorption capacity, density etc. All this lead to the formulation of a new concrete which could replace the ancient type.

Fig. 2: Cross section of a drilling core with the typical composition of a concrete with high amount on blast furnace slag. Size: 5x 12 cm

Fig. 3: Cross section of a drilling core with the raster for image analysis. Picture size: 10x15 cm

Very important for repairing concrete in historic buildings: surface structures and types of surface treatment. Neither in Voelklingen nor in Hattingen, we found any special surface treatment with stonemason’s tools, like in other buildings of a similar age. Here, the structure of the form-boards was the only, but very typical feature of the surface.

Fig. 4: Concrete surface during the remediation. Very distinct pattern of form boards

Fig. 5: Concrete surface after repairing, reprofiling and staining.

The way to this aim can be described in three different steps which can be seen in the following figures:

Fig. 6: Three steps of reprofiling concrete surface, using forming boards in the same size as found on the original concrete surface.

All these steps serve to reach only one aim: a durable concrete repair, retaining all the original structures and characteristics of the surface. All experience shows that these methods are not more expensive than the “standard“ concrete repair, completely following EN 1504.

The reason for this surprising fact: Only single spots of the concrete surface are treated. There is no “over all“ sand blasting or water jetting. There is no complete covering with PCC-mortars and/or coloured coatings. As result, we have a concrete building with an improved resistance against carbonation and deterioration which preserves all its characteristic features on the surface.

Fig. 7-8: Corner of the ore bunker in the UNESCO World Heritage Voelklingen Ironworks, before (left) and after (right) concrete repair. Performance of the reprofiling is nearly invisible, the typical red-brownish, rusty colour of the surface is adjusted to the remaining original surrounding